

PEDAGOGICAL CONDITIONS FOR ACTIVATING STUDENTS' OUTSIDE-COURSE LEARNING ACTIVITIES THROUGH DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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Abstract. *This article clarifies the concept of pedagogical conditions and proposes pedagogical conditions for activating students' extracurricular educational activities using digital technologies.*

Keywords: *digital technology, pedagogical condition, mobile technology, information and educational environment, educational platform, website.*

In general secondary schools, adherence to pedagogical conditions is of great importance in activating students' extracurricular activities. Properly selected and systematically implemented pedagogical conditions allow achieving high results in practical activities with the teacher and the learner at different levels of the educational process [1].

Therefore, it is necessary to clarify the pedagogical conditions for activating students' extracurricular activities. To this end, it is first considered appropriate to clarify the meaning of the concept of "pedagogical condition" and determine its functions in programming languages, based on an analysis of scientific and methodological literature.

The concept of pedagogical conditions is discussed in the works of N.G. Bajenova [2], I.V. Khludeyeva [2], V. Kupriyanov [3], S.A. Dinina [3], which summarize and define various groups of conditions. These scientists argue that, depending on the nature of the impact, there are objective and subjective conditions, and according to the specific characteristics of the object of impact, there are general and private conditions, as well as spatial and others.

Some researchers and scientists associate pedagogical conditions with the pedagogical system (N.V. Ippolitova [4], S.N. Pavlov [5], A.Kh. Khushbakhtov [6], etc.). The authors conclude that pedagogical conditions are one of the components of the pedagogical system, reflecting the totality of the possibilities of the educational and material-spatial environment, which have a personal and procedural impact. Aspects of this system are to ensure its effective functioning and development.

According to U.M. Mirsanov, pedagogical conditions are a set of specially based, organized circumstances and directions of pedagogical activity that determine the educational process, its various stages, and the achievement of educational effectiveness in general [7].

Based on this definition, the pedagogical conditions for activating students' extracurricular activities through digital technologies were identified:

1. To form a culture of using the global network among students;
2. Encourage students to use mobile technologies for educational resources;
3. To develop students' skills in using information and educational environments, educational platforms, and educational websites related to biology during extracurricular hours;
4. To develop the competence of biology teachers in organizing students' extracurricular activities using cloud services and learning environments.

Thus, by implementing the above conditions, a culture of effective use of the global network and mobile technologies will be formed among secondary school students. It also helps to effectively organize extracurricular activities in biology. As a result, students' interest in biology is increased and their ability to learn independently is developed.

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